

Kinetics of oxidation of L-cystine by pyridinium bromochromate

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Manuscript received 21 September 2007, accepted 21 January 2008

Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of cystine by pyridinium bromochromate (PBC) was studied spectrophotometrically under pseudo-first order conditions in perchloric acid medium at 370 nm. It was found that the reaction is first order in [PBC], fractional order in [cystine] and the reaction rate is increased with $[H^+]$ showing an order of more than unity. Product analysis confirmed cysteic acid as the final product of oxidation.

Keywords : Oxidation of cystine, pyridinium bromochromate.

Introduction

Although the kinetic investigations on the oxidation of cysteine has been thorough, the oxidation of cystine has received a little attention. Very few reports are available on the oxidation of cystine by iodine¹, alkaline permanganate² and potassium ferrate³. Pyridinium bromochromate is a mild and selective oxidant and has been used in the oxidation of a number of organic compounds like benzhydrol⁴, methionine⁵, oxalic acid⁶, formic acid⁶, aliphatic aldehydes⁷, aliphatic alcohols⁸, thioacids⁹, glycine¹⁰, alanine, valine, isoleucine, norleucine and phenyl alanine¹¹. In continuation of our earlier work¹² on the oxidation of cystine by different oxidants, in an attempt to evaluate its degradation mechanism and products, we have attempted to investigate the kinetics of oxidation of cystine by pyridinium bromochromate (PBC) in aqueous perchloric acid medium the results of which are presented in this article.

Results and discussion

Known amounts of cystine were allowed to react completely with a known excess of PBC at 40 °C in 0.8 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄ and after 12 h the residual [PBC] in each case was determined. As per these results the stoichiometry was found to correspond to the equation

The product analysis was carried out chromatographically. The *rf* value is found to be 0.15 which confirms the presence of cysteic acid. The test for free radicals was carried out and the absence of precipitate even after 24 h

is confirmed that no free radicals are found during the reaction. Chromium(III), one of the products was found to have no effect on the reaction rate. The effect of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction was studied by varying it from 0.8–1.5 mol dm⁻³ using sodium perchlorate, keeping the concentration of all other reagents in the reaction mixture constant. It was found that ionic strength (*I*) has negligible effect on the rate of the reaction (Table 1).

The order of the reaction with respect to PBC was determined by varying the concentration of PBC from 0.5–2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ keeping the concentrations of all other species constant. Plots of log (absorbance) versus time were good straight lines, indicating that the order with respect to [PBC] to be unity. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants, *k'* obtained at different concentrations of PBC were found to remain constant confirming first order dependence on [PBC] (Table 1).

Dependence on [cystine], was carried out by varying the concentration of cystine and keeping the concentrations of all other species constant. The data presented in Table 1 show that the pseudo-first order rate constant increases with increase in [cystine] and the order with respect to cystine was found to be fractional. The effect of $[H^+]$ on the rate of the reaction was studied keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant and varying the $[H^+]$ with perchloric acid over the range 0.50–1.00 mol dm⁻³ (Table 1). It was observed that the rate of the reaction increases with increase in $[H^+]$ and the order in $[H^+]$ was found to be more than unity. Further, addition of pyridine does not alter the reaction rate indicating that PBC is not hydrolysed during the reaction.

Table 1. Effect of [PBC], [cystine], [H⁺] and ionic strength, *I*, on the pseudo-first order rate constant, *k'*, at 40 ± 0.1 °C

[PBC] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Cystine] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] × 10 (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>I</i> (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>k'</i> × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
0.50	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.38
0.75	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.21
1.00	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.98
1.50	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.21
2.00	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.38
2.50	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.21
1.00	1.0	8.0	1.0	3.84
1.00	3.0	8.0	1.0	6.40
1.00	5.0	8.0	1.0	7.68
1.00	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.98
1.00	9.0	8.0	1.0	12.47
1.00	7.0	5.0	1.2	4.79
1.00	7.0	6.0	1.2	5.37
1.00	7.0	7.0	1.2	7.68
1.00	7.0	8.0	1.2	9.98
1.00	7.0	9.0	1.2	11.51
1.00	7.0	10.0	1.2	15.35
1.00	7.0	8.0	0.8	9.98
1.00	7.0	8.0	0.9	9.96
1.00	7.0	8.0	1.0	9.94
1.00	7.0	8.0	1.2	9.96
1.00	7.0	8.0	1.4	9.97
1.00	7.0	8.0	1.5	9.98

L-Cystine (-SCH₂CHNH₂COOH)₂ is a sulphur containing amino acid and it possesses four pK_a values. Two of them corresponding to the carboxylic groups (COOH)₁ = 1.51, (COOH)₂ = 2.79 and the other two for amino groups (NH₃⁺)₁ = 8.25 and (NH₃⁺)₂ = 8.97. Under the present experimental conditions, ([H⁺] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³) cystine exists in the form of HOOC(NH₃⁺)CH-CH₂-S-S-CH₂-CH(NH₃⁺)COOH(cystine²⁺) to the extent of 96.3% and as ⁻OOC(NH₃⁺)CH-CH₂-S-S-CH₂-CH(NH₃⁺)COOH(cystine⁺) to the extent of 3.7%.

Based on these observations, cystine²⁺ is presumed to be the reactive species and the following mechanism is proposed.

where R = HOOC(NH₃⁺)CH₂CH-

The above mechanism leads to the rate law

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{PBC}]}{dt} = k[\text{C}] \quad (9)$$

$$= kK_3[\text{cystine}^{2+}][\text{H}_2\text{PBC}]$$

$$= \frac{kK_1K_2K_3[\text{cystine}^{2+}][\text{PBC}]_t[\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1K_2K_3[\text{cystine}^{2+}][\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (10)$$

The rate equation explains the observed first order dependence on [PBC] and fractional order dependence on [cystine].

Taking reciprocals on both sides of eq. (10)

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{[\text{cystine}^{2+}]} \left\{ \frac{1}{kK_1K_2K_3[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{1}{kK_2K_3[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{kK_3} \right\} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (11)$$

From eq. (11), a plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{cystine}]$ should be a straight line with a positive intercept on Y-axis. Similar plots (Fig. 1) were obtained experimentally when cystine variation studies were carried out at three different temperatures (35, 40 and 45 °C) thus supporting the proposed mechanism. Further, it is also possible to calculate the values of k from the corresponding intercepts. Hence, the activation parameters of the rate determining step

were computed and the values of E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were found to be $20.2 \pm 1.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-242.09 \pm 19.1 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The negative entropy indicates that the transition state is rigid in nature.

Experimental

Stock solution of L-cystine (Himedia) was prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of cystine in perchloric acid. PBC was prepared and its purity checked by the usual method¹⁴. Kinetic measurements were carried out at $40 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in 0.8 mol dm^{-3} perchloric acid medium under the conditions $[\text{H}^+] > [\text{cystine}] > [\text{PBC}]$. The progress of the reaction was followed by measuring the absorbance of PBC at 370 nm using Milton Roy 1201 UV-Visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm silica cells. The temperature is kept constant using a SISKIN JULABO V constant temperature liquid circulatory bath. The rate constants were found to be reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

In order to carryout the product analysis, the chromatographic plate was spotted with the reaction product and it was saturated with vapours of phenol and then it was run in water-saturated phenol. After the development of the chromatogram, the plate was removed from the tank and dried. It was then sprayed with 1% solution of ninhydrin in *n*-butanol and heated in an oven for five minutes at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The test for free radicals was carried out by taking cystine, perchloric acid in a thumberg tube and acryloni-

Fig. 1. Plot of $1/k'$ versus $1/[\text{cystine}]$ at three different temperatures.

Note

trile and PBC in a bent tube. After evacuating the system the solutions are mixed by tilting the tube. The reaction mixture was kept aside and even after 24 h no precipitate was observed.

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